

Prevalence of Severity of Anaemia among Non-Pregnant Reproductive Age Group Females in Hilly Region of Thally Block, Krishnagiri District, Tamil Nadu, India: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Background: Anemia, characterized by insufficient red blood cells to meet physiological needs, is a significant public health issue in India, particularly among marginalized groups such as women in tribal villages.

Objectives: Objective of this study is to estimate the prevalence of anemia among non-pregnant women of reproductive age in tribal areas and identify associated factors.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted over six months, involving 1050 non-pregnant women of reproductive age in the hilly Thally block, Krishnagiri Health Unit District. Data were collected using an interviewer-administered semi-structured questionnaire, covering height, weight, blood grouping, BMI, blood pressure, capillary blood glucose levels, and hemoglobin levels via the cyanmethemoglobin method (Drapkin solution). The WHO criteria for anemia severity were applied to evaluate prevalence.

Results: Among the 1050 women, the prevalence of anemia was 45.90% (n=482). According to WHO criteria, 1.05% (n=11) were severely anemic, with 27.27% (n=3) of them being undernourished. Additionally, 21.14% (n=222) were moderately anemic, of which 25.68% (n=57) were undernourished, and 23.71% (n=249) were mildly anemic, with 19.68% (n=49) undernourished.

Conclusion: To alleviate anemia among reproductive-age women in hilly regions, regular screening should extend beyond pregnant women to all women of reproductive age. Prophylactic drug administration, tailored health education on nutrition and hygiene, and other appropriate interventions should be implemented to address their specific needs. This approach aims to significantly reduce the anemia burden in this vulnerable population.

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Introduction

Anemia is a significant public health issue that affects countries regardless of their income levels [1]. It is particularly common among women of reproductive age [2]. Anemia is characterized by a low blood hemoglobin (Hb) concentration and can result from various factors such as deficiencies in iron and other micronutrients, acute and chronic infections, and both inherited and acquired disorders [1].

Individuals with anemia typically exhibit symptoms like fatigue, breathlessness, dizziness, and headaches [3]. Additionally, anemia increases vulnerability to various infections and diminishes work capacity [4]. The severity of anemia correlates with the intensity of its symptoms, and severe anemia can lead to complications such as infections and heart failure [5,6].

The standard hemoglobin cut-off level for diagnosing anemia in non-pregnant females aged 15 years and above is 12.0 g/dL. However, this cut-off can

vary based on factors such as gender, age, ethnicity, pregnancy, smoking behavior, altitude, and geography. It is estimated that approximately 24.8% of the global population is affected by anemia [7].

Anemia among women of reproductive age (WRA) is rising at an alarming rate, with a prevalence of 33%. This issue is emphasized in Sustainable Development Goal 2.2, which focuses on the nutritional needs of lactating mothers, pregnant women, and adolescent girls [8]. The time between menarche and menopause presents a higher risk for anemia due to blood loss during menstruation [9].

Despite considerable efforts, two-thirds of women of reproductive age in India continue to suffer from some form of anemia, whether mild, moderate, or severe. While it is important to address all types of anemia, moderate and severe anemia in non-pregnant women should receive particular attention, as these forms are associated with significant health consequences [10].

Materials and Methods

This community-based cross-sectional study was conducted from August 2023 to January 2024, among women in the reproductive age group in the villages in the Thally block, Krishnagiri district, Tamil Nadu, India. The study subjects were selected by cluster sampling method. Sample size was calculated based on the prevalence of anemia among reproductive age group women (55.9%) [11], with an allowable error of 20% and a design effect of 3, the sample size was estimated as 945, and considering a 10% refusal rate, the sample size was arrived at 1050.

Every tribal village in the Thally was considered as a cluster. 21 tribal villages of them were selected by simple random method. In each selected village, 50 subjects (21 village's \times 50 = 1050 subjects) were to be selected. By systematic sampling method, in each village, the houses were selected. However, if more than one such woman were available in the selected house, all of them were included. Non-pregnant women in the reproductive age group who are willing to participate in the study only were included. Pregnant women and those with any other chronic medical illness like thyroid or known cases of any other blood disorders were excluded. Hence, a total of 1050 women were studied. Ethical committee clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of the Directorate of Public Health and Preventive Medicine, Chennai. After obtaining written informed consent, each study participant was interviewed by using a pre-tested interviewer-administered semi-structured questionnaire, and the data were recorded in a separate proforma for each study participant.

The following data was collected from the study participants, height, weight, blood grouping, BMI, BP, and hemoglobin using the cynometh method (Drapkin solution). WHO severity of Anemia criteria was followed and prevalence of Anemia was evaluated. The descriptive data were expressed as Mean & Standard deviation for continuous variables and Frequency & Percentage for categorical variables. The chi-square test was applied to find out the association between unmet need and various factors and $p < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant.

Results

Age distribution of the study participants reveals that the majority of the them were between 25-34 years ($n=530$, 50%), followed by 35-44 years ($n=318$, 30%), 15-24 years ($n=192$, 18%), and a small proportion above 44 years ($n=10$, 1%). Regarding the number of children, a significant majority had 1-3 children ($n=871$, 83%), while very

few had more than 3 children ($n=12$, 1%), no children ($n=79$, 7.5%), or were not married ($n=88$, 8%).

In terms of occupation, 94% ($n=989$) of the participants were not working, while only 6% ($n=61$) were employed. Obesity grading indicated that 50% ($n=520$) had normal weight, 22% ($n=232$) were pre-obese, 20% ($n=211$) were underweight, and smaller proportions were classified as obese-1 ($n=70$, 7%), obese-2 ($n=14$, 1%), or obese-3 ($n=3$, 0.3%). Awareness about the importance of mixing pulses and cereals for a balanced diet was low, with 77% ($n=804$) unaware and only 23% ($n=246$) aware. Similarly, awareness regarding birth spacing was also limited, with 62% ($n=650$) unaware and 38% ($n=400$) aware.

The prevalence of anemia among the study population is 45.9% ($n=482$). As per WHO-Anemia severity grading, anemia grading, 23.71% ($n=249$) had mild anemia, 21.14% ($n=222$) had moderate anemia, and 1.05% ($n=11$) had severe anemia. Figure 1 presents the prevalence of anemia as per WHO criteria. Table 1 presents the socio-demographic characteristics and their awareness levels of the 1050 study subjects.

The distribution across age groups did not show a significant association with anemia severity ($p=0.091$). The chi-square test showed no significant association between occupation and anemia severity ($p=0.112$). Both working and non-working women had similar distributions across anemia severities.

There was no significant association between obesity grading and anemia severity ($p=0.206$). However, underweight individuals had a higher percentage of severe anemia cases compared to other groups. Awareness regarding the importance of mixing pulses and cereals did not significantly affect anemia severity ($p=0.156$). Both aware and unaware groups had similar distributions across anemia severities.

A significant association was found between parity and anemia severity ($p=0.001$). Women with 1-3 children had more severe anemia cases compared to other groups. Awareness regarding birth spacing was significantly associated with anemia severity ($p=0.012$). Women who were unaware of birth spacing practices had a higher prevalence of severe anemia. Table 2 explores the association between various socio-demographic factors and the severity of anemia, using the WHO classification.

In conclusion, while most socio-demographic factors showed no significant association with the severity of anemia, parity and awareness regarding birth spacing were significantly related, suggesting the need for targeted interventions in these areas.

Table 1: Socio-demographic details of the study subjects (n=1050)

Socio-demographic factors	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (in years)		
15-24	192	18%
25-34	530	50%
35-44	318	30%
>44	10	1%
No of children		
1- to 3	871	83%
More than 3	12	1%
No children	79	7.5%
Not married	88	8%
Occupation		
Working	61	6%
Not working	989	94%
Obesity grading		
Underweight	211	20%
Normal	520	50%
Pre-obese	232	22%
Obese-1	70	7%
Obese-2	14	1%
Obese-3	3	0.3%
Knowledge about the importance of mixing pulses and cereals for a balanced diet		
Unaware	804	77%
Aware	246	23%
Awareness regarding birth spacing		
Unaware	650	62%
Aware	400	38%
Anemia grading		
Less than 8 (severe anemia)	11	1%
8-10.9 (moderate anemia)	222	21%
11-11.9 (mild anemia)	249	24%
More than 12 (non-anemia)	568	54%

Table 2: Association between Socio-demographic factors and Severity of Anemia (n=1050)

Variables	WHO - Severity of Anemia				p-value by Chi-square test statistics
	Severe	Moderate	Mild	Non-Anemic	
Age in years					
15-24	1 (9.09%)	44 (19.82%)	46 (18.47%)	101 (17.78%)	0.091
25-34	6 (54.55%)	109 (49.1%)	139 (55.8%)	276 (48.59%)	
35-44	3 (27.27%)	66 (29.73%)	62 (24.9%)	187 (32.92%)	
>44	1 (9.09%)	3 (1.35%)	2 (0.81%)	4 (0.7%)	
Occupation					
Working	0 (0%)	9 (4.05%)	10 (4.02%)	42 (7.39%)	0.112
Not working	11 (100%)	213 (95.9%)	239 (95.9%)	526 (92.61%)	
Obesity Grading					
Underweight	3 (27.27%)	57 (25.68%)	49 (19.68%)	102 (17.96%)	0.206
Normal	6 (54.55%)	110 (49.6%)	119 (47.8%)	285 (50.18%)	
Pre-obese	1 (9.09%)	45 (20.27%)	60 (24.1%)	126 (22.18%)	
Obese-1	0 (0%)	9 (4.05%)	18 (7.23%)	43 (7.57%)	
Obese-2	1 (9.09%)	1 (0.45%)	2 (0.81%)	10 (1.76%)	
Obese-3	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (0.4%)	2 (0.35%)	
Awareness regarding the importance of mixing pulses and cereals for a balanced diet					
Unaware	8 (72.73%)	159 (71.6%)	188 (75.5%)	449 (79.04%)	0.156
Aware	3 (27.27%)	63 (28.38%)	61 (24.5%)	119 (20.96%)	
Parity					
1-3	8 (72.73%)	192 (86.5%)	199 (79.9%)	472 (83.1%)	
More than 3	3 (27.27%)	1 (0.45%)	4 (1.61%)	4 (0.7%)	

No children	0 (0%)	12 (5.41%)	26 (10.44%)	41 (7.2%)	0.001*
Not married	0 (0%)	17 (7.66%)	20 (8.03%)	51 (8.98%)	
Awareness regarding birth spacing					
Unaware	7 (63.64%)	123 (55.4%)	143 (57.4%)	377 (50.92%)	0.012*
Aware	4 (36.36%)	99 (44.59%)	106 (42.6%)	191 (49.08%)	
Total	11 (1.05%)	222 (21.14%)	249(23.71%)	568 (54.1%)	

* $p < 0.05$ -statistical significance

Figure 1: Prevalence of Anemia among the study population as per WHO-criteria (n=1050)

Discussion

As per WHO, Prevalence of anemia among women of reproductive age (% of women ages 15-49) in India was 53.00 as of 2019. Its highest value over the past 19 years was 54.20 in 2005, while its lowest value was 52.60 in 2016 [12]. In a Karnataka study done in 2013 among tribal reproductive age group women, it was noted that the prevalence of anemia was 55.9% [11]. In Haryana study in 2012 observed that the prevalence of anemia among reproductive age group women was 96.8% [13]. This cross-sectional study among the non-pregnant tribal women of reproductive age in villages of the hilly block - Thally region of Tamil Nadu found the prevalence of anemia to be 45.9%. This is lower than the 57.2% anemia prevalence among reproductive age non-pregnant women of in India [14] and marginally higher than the district prevalence of 44.3%, as estimated in the NFHS-5 report [15]. However, it is still indicative of a moderate public health problem as per WHO criteria [16]. The prevalence is comparable to a 55.9% figure noted in a 2013 Karnataka study [11], Kadam et al., 2013 among tribal populations. The lower prevalence in our study may be attributable to population characteristics and methodology. The

Karnataka study setting was more purely tribal and vulnerability to undernutrition may have been higher. Earlier studies have also reported a high anemia burden among disadvantaged Indian subgroups. A 2010 hospital-based study found up to 52% moderate-severe anemia among pregnant women in north India [17]. A 2008 study demonstrated correlations between low socioeconomic status and anemia in central Indian children [18].

The proportion with mild, moderate, and severe anemia in our study was 24%, 21%, and 1% respectively. The National Family Health Survey (NFHS) 2015-16 (IIPS & ICF, 2017) found that in Tamil Nadu the proportions were 22.7% mild, 2.5% moderate, and 0.3% severe. Thus moderate anemia rates are notably higher in this tribal hilly setting compared to the state average. This agrees with the expectation that nutritional deficiency anemia has a higher prevalence in socioeconomically challenged populations [4]. Like most other works [4,11,17-19], the likelihood and severity of anemia in our subjects also showed a positive association with undernutrition indicators. Programs should focus screening and management on this high-risk subgroup. An interesting finding

was the association between parity, lack of spacing awareness, and anemia severity, consistent with studies from India and Africa [20,21]. Repeated pregnancy cycles can strain iron stores. Educating women on spacing benefits may help reduce anemia prevalence. Overall, this study provides updated data about the persistence of the nutritional anemia challenge among vulnerable Indian subgroups. Context-tailored nutritional interventions and active community-based screening should remain priority public health actions in tribal areas as recommended globally [1,22].

The strength of the study is an appropriate sample size however, some other important factors like their menstrual cycle and other cultural factors were not evaluated.

Conclusion

The prevalence of anemia was estimated to be 45.9% (n=482) in this study. The severity of anemia is as follows:

- 23.71% were mild of which 20.08% were undernourished
- 21.14% were moderate of which 26.58% were undernourished
- 1.05 % were severe of which 27.27% were undernourished

The study concludes that women residing in hilly regions are more prone to developing anemia, primarily due to nutritional deprivation. This is especially evident in women with higher parity and poor awareness regarding birth spacing. Therefore, it is imperative to implement iron supplementation programs and increase awareness about birth spacing and parity levels among all reproductive-age women in the hilly region of Thally. Tailor-made approaches are necessary, particularly for tribal areas, to effectively address these issues and reduce the burden of anemia.

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